

1 Supplementary File 1

2 The database PubMed was explored to search for original articles describing plasmin substrates. To
3 this end, the following search terms were applied: “(plasmin[Title]) AND (cleav*[Title])”,
4 “(plasmin[Title]) AND (degrad*[Title])” and “(plasmin[Title]) AND (hydrol*[Title])”; which
5 yielded 90, 148 and 29 results, respectively (as of 10th October 2024). After a manual pre-selection
6 of relevant articles based on their titles, and excluding those for which access was unavailable, a total
7 of 186 articles were considered for further analysis. Additionally, some references not containing the
8 specified search terms were incorporated based on prior knowledge of the topic or because they were
9 identified as relevant during the elaboration of the main text. **Supplementary Table 1** provides a
10 summary of all plasmin substrates described in these articles, along with the associated physiological
11 relevance of this proteolytic event, whether experimentally demonstrated or not. Only articles
12 describing physiological plasmin substrates were included; studies describing engineered substrates
13 and/or plasmin cleavage events with potential applications in the food industry were excluded.

Supplementary Table 1. Fibrinolysis-unrelated plasmin substrates.		
Substrate	Physiological relevance	PMID (a)
Aggrecan	coagulation (platelet aggregation)	2148055
α -2-macroglobulin (α 2M)	α 2M clearance from plasma	2435319
Amyloid β -protein	amyloidosis (including Alzheimer's Disease)	32694536; 11588612; 10471309
	production of non-amyloidogenic fragments, protection against the development of Alzheimer's disease	12446968
Amyloid β -protein (aggregates)	prevents amyloid β -induced neurotoxicity	10818128
Amyloid β -protein (precursor)	amyloidosis (including Alzheimer's Disease)	11263499
Angiopoietin-like protein 4 and 8 (ANGPTL4/8)	triglyceride metabolism	36763533
Angiotensin II	blood pressure	4339394
Annexin A2	inflammation (cytokine production by macrophages)	17413040
	inflammation (intracellular signalling)	16373665
Antibodies (opsonising)	immune evasion (<i>Francisella tularensis</i>)	19752236
Antibodies (IgG)	IgG metabolism (regulation of adaptive immune responses)	8037734
β -2-glycoprotein (β 2GPI)	angiogenesis (inhibition)	17872974
	thrombosis	9596664
β -glycan	signalling by type I and type II TGF- β	8068006

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Substrate	Physiological relevance	PMID (a)
Brain-derived neurotrophic factor, precursor (pro-BDNF)	hypocampal plasticity (long-term memory)	15486301
C1 inhibitor	pathology of inflammatory disorders (systemic lupus erythematosus, respiratory distress syndrome, rheumatoid arthritis)	9234243
C3	leukocyte chemotaxis, increase in vascular permeability	4226271
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>)	23071827
	chemotaxis of mast cells and neutrophils (by C3a and C5a)	20870944
	leukocyte chemotaxis (by C3a and C5a), activation of complement system (induction of membrane attack complex (MAC) assembly)	27077125
C3b	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>S. aureus</i>)	23071827
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>)	22124123
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>Leptospira interrogans</i> , invasion)	26822552
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>)	26099590
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by pathogenic bacteria)	22451663
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>)	26945067
C3b proteolytic fragment (iC3b)	complement pathway regulation	25556624
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>S. pyogenes</i>)	26945067
C5	chemotaxis of mast cells and neutrophils (by C3a and C5a)	20870944
	leukocyte chemotaxis (by C3a and C5a), activation of complement system (induction of membrane attack complex (MAC) assembly)	27077125
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion strategy by <i>M. catarrhalis</i>)	26099590
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by pathogenic bacteria)	22451663
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>L. interrogans</i> , invasion)	26822552
Cadherin-5 (VE-cadherin)	<i>S. pneumoniae</i> epithelial migration	18725422
Casein	digestion of milk components during lactation	6240266
		1369431;
		13885559
C-C motif chemokine ligand 1 (CCL1/HCC-1)	inflammation, generation of a truncated variant that stimulates leukocyte chemotaxis	11544332
C-C motif chemokine ligand 2 (CCL2) (b)	enhances CCL2 chemotactic activities, excitotoxic neurodegeneration	17301181
	inflammation (central nervous system)	21486949
C-C motif chemokine ligand 21 (CCL21)	inflammation, generation of a truncated variant that stimulates dendritic cell chemotaxis	35690148
	lymphocyte migration, immune cell adhesion	27301418
Chromogranin A	cardiovascular disease (hypertension)	17991725
	cell adhesion (neuroendocrine tumours)	12297497
	stress-related catecholamine responses mediated by neuroendocrine cells	11342539
Collagen type IV (c)	skeletal muscle degeneration	2947809
	tumour invasion	2144209
Collagen type XIX ECM	Release of fragment NC1(XIX), which has anti-tumour activities	25668817
	capillary morphogenesis (vessel formation)	30784190
	human endometrial stromal cell viability, proliferation, and migration (development of endometriosis)	38735446
	ECM degradation, migration of <i>S. pneumoniae</i>	16113819
	pathological ECM accumulation, glomerulonephritis	16788698
	metastatic potential of thyroid tumour cell line	10524570

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Substrate	Physiological relevance	PMID (a)
Epithelial sodium channel (ENaC)	glomerular ECM accumulation, renal disease	7540230
	renal disorders (proteinuria)	18981180
	general ENaC functions	22966015
	pulmonary blood-gas exchange (lung oedema)	32133621
Factor VIII	coagulation	19126539; 4274479; 17189254; 6444272
Factor Xa (FXa)	coagulation	8663221
Fibrin (d)(e)	angiogenesis	12197472
	angiogenesis (inhibition of tubule formation by endothelial cells) [B β 43-63]	20068569
	angiogenesis (inhibits endothelial cell migration and tubule formation), [fragment E]	10987275
	angiogenesis (inhibits the migration and tubule formation of human dermal microvascular endothelial cells) [alphastatin]	14512300
	angiogenesis [fragment E]	1280677
	coagulation (increased tissue factor production), fibrinolysis (increases u-PA production), inflammation (increased IL-1 secretion), [D-dimer]	1845845
	diagnosis of coagulation and thrombolytic disorders	4265363
	ECM degradation, migration of <i>S. pneumoniae</i>	16113819
	endothelial barrier integrity (reduces vascular leakage during shock) [B β 15-42]	19401765
	inflammation (inhibits leukocyte transmigration during myocardial ischemia-reperfusion injury) [B β 15-42]	12663071
	inflammation (neutrophil and fibroblast chemotaxis) [B β 1-42]	3359049
	inflammation (IL-6 production by macrophages) [fragment E]	10102564
	inflammation (production of IL-6 and IL-1 β by monocytes) [D-dimer]	8199021
	mitigates pathology associated to ischemia/reperfusion (reduces leukocyte infiltration) [B β 15-42]	20405575; 19114899
	pathology of anti-phospholipid syndrome	15100323
	smooth muscle cell migration and proliferation (restenosis and atherogenesis) [fragment E]	10713318
	tumour progression of oral squamous cell carcinoma [B β 15-42]	15723073
	wound healing	28135202
	wound healing, cell adhesion, inflammation (increased IL-1 β production) [fragment E]	11266115
	human endometrial stromal cell viability, proliferation, and migration (development of endometriosis)	38735446
ovarian cancer progression	2139349	
Fibrinogen (d)	antigenic properties of fibrin(ogen) degradation products (FDPs)	17561232; 4258329
	coagulation	128845; 94836; 4262076; 236019
	complement system inhibition (immune evasion by <i>L. interrogans</i> , invasion)	26822552
	cytotoxicity on kidney cells	6857591
	progression of sarcoma (in mice)	6459937
	postoperative recovery from hepatectomy (relevance of FDPs)	2156347
	production of vasoactive peptides	7353036
	vasoconstriction/dilation by FDPs	155325
	fibroblast proliferation, tissue repair	8789459
	ECM degradation, migration of <i>S. pneumoniae</i>	16113819
Fibroblast growth factor 2 (FGF-2)	fibroblast proliferation, tissue repair	8789459
Fibronectin	ECM degradation, migration of <i>S. pneumoniae</i>	16113819

Supplementary Table 1. Fibrinolysis-unrelated plasmin substrates.		
Substrate	Physiological relevance	PMID (a)
	invasion, migration (<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i>)	10417158
	phagocytosis	7252334
	vitroretinal surgery	20450255
	tumour metastasis	2947330
	skeletal muscle degeneration	2947809
Fragment E	clinical applications (distinguish between fibrinolysis and fibrinogenolysis)	6449096
Gammaglobulins	treatment of adult autoimmune thrombocytopenic purpura	6683424
Growth hormone	all growth hormone-related functions, including glucose uptake	10702910
		4234815
Hemagglutinin (of <i>Influenza virus</i>)	virus entry	6461136; 4795670
High density lipoprotein (HDL)	development of atherosclerosis	6460340
Histidine-rich glycoprotein (HRG)	cell adhesion, angiogenesis, coagulation, fibrinolysis and clearance of immune complexes, necrotic cells and pathogens	19712047; 38272220
Insulin-like growth factor-binding protein-5 (IGFBP-5)	bone remodelling	9374687
Interferon (gamma)	interferon gamma-mediated immune responses	2529320
Interleukin 8 (IL-8)	neutrophil chemotaxis	1828038
Kallikrein	formation of active fragments with potential to regulate coagulation	2949543
Kininogen	acetaminophen (APAP)-induced liver injury	33827130
	coagulation (contact mediated clotting and activation of factor XII)	157559
Lactoglobulin (β)	food industry applications	10552596; 10552597
Laminin	ECM degradation, migration of <i>S. pneumoniae</i>	16113819
	epidermal BM assembly and differentiation	18460030
	invasion, migration (<i>B. burgdorferi</i>)	10417158
	long-term potentiation	10684901
	neuronal degeneration	9428515
	tissue remodelling, wound healing	6455777
	vitroretinal surgery	20450255
	tumour metastasis	2947330
	skeletal muscle degeneration	2947809
	macrophage protease expression	11827968
MMP (collagenase, not specified)	osteoid removal by osteoblasts	2554972
MMP-2	pathologies related to MMP-2 dysregulation	9679953
Myelin	demyelinating pathologies	6167674
	inflammatory demyelinating diseases	2936427; 2411869
Neural cell adhesion molecule L1	neural development and regeneration	10574721
NR2A subunit of N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDA)	disorders of the central nervous system, including ischemia and spinal cord injury	19240037
Osteopontin	integrin-mediated cell adhesion, bone mineralization, inhibition of ectopic calcification, wound healing, inflammation, regulation of immune cell functions, and tumour growth	20071328
Perlecan	release of bound basic FGF (angiogenesis)	8626565
Glycoproteins GPIIb-IIIa, GPIb, GPIa-Iia	platelet aggregation, acute myocardial infarction	2169924
Prolactin, placental lactogen	pregnancy-related endothelial cell dysfunctions (preeclampsia)	34601001
Pro-MMP-1	collagen degradation, wound healing	10733668
	ECM (collagen) degradation in physiological and pathological conditions (g)	2176865

Supplementary Table 1. Fibrinolysis-unrelated plasmin substrates.		
Substrate	Physiological relevance	PMID (a)
	ECM degradation in the skin	29498767
	ECM degradation, vascular regression	15870107
pro-MMP-2 (h)	potentially all MMP-2 physiologic roles	9089282
pro-MMP-3	ECM degradation, aneurism formation	9398846
	ECM degradation, tumour cell invasion (MDA-MB-231 breast carcinoma cell line)	10224058
	tumour cell invasion (MDA-MB-231 breast carcinoma cell line)	10415742
Pro-MMP-9	degradation of pro-MMP-9 upon pre-treatment with divalent cation chelators, inactivation of its functions (inflammation, metastasis)	22677171
	inflammation (macrophage invasion) (f)	20424186
	ECM degradation, aneurism formation (f)	9398846
Pro-MMP-10	mediates thrombin-dependent vascular effects	19762781
Pro-MMP-12	ECM degradation, aneurism formation	9398846
Pro-MMP-13	ECM degradation, aneurism formation	9398846
Protease-activated receptors (PARs)	inflammation (monocyte recruitment)	25165151
	coagulation (platelet aggregation)	14973136; 10610687
Proteoglycan	degradation of arterial connective tissue	2969314
	cartilage destruction associated with rheumatoid arthritis	6235859
Pro-u-PA	tumour cell metastasis	1837419
SARS-CoV-2 Spike	SARS-CoV-2 cell entry	36193902
Syndecan-4	arteriosclerosis (development of arteriosclerotic plaques), recruitment of mononuclear blood cells to the plaque	16087677
Synuclein (α)	Parkinson's disease	22619171
Thrombin receptor	platelet activation	8760030
Trypsin inhibitor (inter- α)	inflammation, kidney injury	92450
Tumour necrosis factor α (TNF- α)	ovulation (sheep)	10208979
u-PA receptor (uPAR)	potentially all u-PA functions (inflammatory, tumour invasion, others)	15358545
Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)	angiogenesis	12417332
Vitronectin	invasion, migration (<i>B. burgdorferi</i>)	10417158
von Willebrand factor	coagulation	3160727; 38271661; 28279966; 24449821; 6444272

14 (a) PubMed identification number. (b) Also known as monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1). (c) Since tissue
15 sections were used for the experiments, the authors suggest that collagen type IV degradation might occur via plasmin-
16 mediated activation of latent collagenase, as demonstrated in Pins *et al.*, 2000. (d) Papers describing plasmin cleavage of
17 fibrinogen or fibrin were included in the table only if this activity was related to non-fibrinolytic functions. (e) The fibrin
18 degradation product (FDP) that exerts the mentioned function is indicated in square brackets. (f) The authors propose
19 direct cleavage of pro-MMP-9 by plasmin, contrasting with the widely accepted mechanism of MMP-9 activation
20 involving plasmin-mediated activation of MMP-3, which subsequently cleaves pro-MMP-9 and activates it. (g) This
21 study shows that plasmin generates a pro-MMP-1 intermediate devoid of catalytic activity that is subsequently activated
22 by MMP-3. (h) Plasmin cleaves and activates an intermediate form of MMP-2 that is generated by MT1-MMP cleavage
23 of pro-MMP-2. Blank cells indicate information that was not reported in the publication. ECM, extracellular matrix;

24 CCL1, C-C motif chemokine ligand 1; CCL2, C-C motif chemokine ligand 2; CCL21, C-C motif chemokine ligand 21;
 25 FDP, fibrin degradation product; FGF, fibroblast growth factor; MMP, metalloprotease; pro-BDNF, precursor of the
 26 brain-derived neurotrophic factor; pro-u-PA, precursor of the urokinase-type plasminogen activator; u-PA, urokinase-
 27 type plasminogen activator; SARS-CoV-2, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2.

28 **Supplementary File 2**

29 Supplementary Table 2 provides an updated compilation of data from Diosdado *et al.*, 2022
 30 (Diosdado *et al.*, 2022) and González-Miguel *et al.*, 2016 (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2016a), which
 31 reviewed parasitic proteins interacting with the PLG/plasmin system employing distinct
 32 methodologies. Studies identifying putative PLG/plasmin-interacting proteins in whole or partial
 33 parasite protein extracts were excluded from this table. Only studies reporting the interaction between
 34 a specific parasitic protein and fibrinolytic factors were considered, demonstrated either through the
 35 use of recombinant proteins (the majority of studies) or via other protein-protein interaction
 36 techniques, such as immunoprecipitation followed by mass spectrometry (IP-MS; for instance, Ref.
 37 (El Chamy Maluf *et al.*, 2020)).

Supplementary Table 2. Parasite-derived proteins that interact with the PLG/plasmin system.						
Protein	Parasite	Fibrinolytic function	Location (a)	Stage (a)	Biological process (b)	Ref. (c)
Actin	<i>Dirofilaria immitis</i>	PLG-R, increase in t-PA/u-PA expression	Surface, ESP, somatic	Adult	Fibrinolysis (d), survival, pathogenesis	25875022
Annexin	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic	Adult, metacercaria	Immune modulation	24861011
	<i>Schistosoma bovis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic	Adult, schistosomula	Survival	21889851
	<i>Spirometra erinaceieuropaei</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic, ESP	Spargana, eggs	Tissue invasion, immune evasion	39601902
	<i>Spirometra erinaceieuropaei</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic, ESP	Adult, spargana	Immune evasion, tissue invasion	39601902
Cathepsin B2	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	PLG-R	Tegument	NEJ	Trans-intestinal migration	37083884
Cathepsin B3	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	PLG-R, pro-u-PA binding	Tegument	NEJ	Trans-intestinal migration	37083884, 39856784
Cathepsin L3	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	PLG-R, pro-u-PA binding	Tegument	NEJ	Trans-intestinal migration	37083884, 39856784

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Protein	Parasite	Fibrinolytic function	Location (a)	Stage (a)	Biological process (b)	Ref. (c)
Enolase	<i>Babesia microti</i>	PLG-R	Surface, cytosol	Intraerythrocytic	Migration, invasion	28443086
	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, ESP	Egg, cercaria, metacercaria, adult	Migration, invasion, immune evasion, pathogenesis	21382423
	<i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>	PLG-R	Surface	Oocyst	Migration, invasion	28569179
	<i>Echinostoma caproni</i>	PLG-R	ESP, somatic	Adult	Establishment and pathogenesis (tissue destruction)	17462631
	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	PLG-R	Surface	NEJ	Migration, adhesion, survival	39213442
		pro-u-PA binding	Surface	NEJ	Trans-intestinal migration	39856784
	<i>Giardia intestinalis</i> (e)	PLG-R			Adhesion to host cells	28770921
	<i>Leishmania mexicana</i>	PLG-R	Surface, EVs	Promastigote	Migration, invasion	23178693, 17653767
	<i>Onchocerca volvulus</i>	PLG-R	Somatic	Larva L3, microfilaria, adult	Migration (ECM degradation)	12818429
	<i>Plasmodium berghei/falciparum</i>	PLG-R	Surface	Ookynete	Development (inside mosquito vector)	21949403
	<i>Schistosoma bovis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic and ESP	Adult	(f)	20609522
	<i>Schistosoma japonicum</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic	Schistosomula, adult	Migration, development	20512506
	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	PLG-R	Surface	Schistosomula, adult	Fibrinolysis, survival	26658895
	<i>Spirometra mansoni</i>	PLG-R	Surface, ESP	Spargana, adult	Tissue invasion	34031713
	<i>Taenia multiceps</i>	PLG-R		Protoscolex, adult		26412520
	<i>Taenia pisiformis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, ESP	Metacestode	Invasion, migration	25623259
<i>Taenia solium</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic	Cysticercus, adult	Migration, invasion, survival	29466706, 29657009	
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	PLG-R	Surface	Larva, adult	Migration, invasion	31806006	
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	PLG-R	Surface		Adhesion, virulence	18070902	
FBAL	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	PLG-R	Somatic, ESP	Adult	Fibrinolysis, survival, nutrition	33612738
	<i>Dirofilaria immitis</i>	PLG-R, increase in t-PA/u-PA expression	Surface, ESP, somatic	Adult	Fibrinolysis, survival, pathogenesis	25875022
Galectin	<i>Dirofilaria immitis</i>	PLG-R, increase in u-PA expression	Surface, ESP, somatic	Adult	Fibrinolysis, survival, pathogenesis	25666684
GAPDH	<i>Babesia microti</i>	PLG-R		Intraerythrocytic	Migration, invasion	31355216

Supplementary Table 2. Parasite-derived proteins that interact with the PLG/plasmin system.						
Protein	Parasite	Fibrinolytic function	Location (a)	Stage (a)	Biological process (b)	Ref. (c)
	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	PLG-R	Surface, somatic	Egg, metacercaria, adult	Migration, invasion	25300416
	<i>Dirofilaria immitis</i>	PLG-R, increase in u-PA expression	Surface, somatic	Adult	Fibrinolysis, survival, pathogenesis	25666684
	<i>Onchocerca volvulus</i>	PLG-R	Somatic	Larva L3, microfilaria, adult	Migration (ECM degradation)	15955451
	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	PLG-R	Surface	Adult	Fibrinolysis, survival	32098782
	<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	PLG-R	Surface		Invasion	19380472
GST	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	pro-u-PA binding	Tegument	NEJ	Trans-intestinal migration	39856784
HSP60 (f)	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	PLG-R, PLG internalization	Cytosol	Intraerythrocytic	Generate ALFs that inhibit inflammatory responses	32847585
LACK	<i>Leishmania mexicana</i>	PLG-R	Surface, secreted	Promastigote	Migration, invasion	21272581
NAPc2	<i>Ancylostoma caninum</i>	decrease u-PA expression				25672417
PGM	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	PLG-R	Tegument	Schistosomula, adult	Fibrinolysis, survival	36083036
Serpin	<i>Echinococcus multicularis</i>	Plasmin inhibition				17727977
SMP-1	<i>Leishmania mexicana</i>	PLG-R	EVs	Promastigote	Migration, invasion	23178693
SP2	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	PA, enhances t-PA activity	Surface (only males), somatic, ESP	Adult	Migration, invasion	29677188
TGH-2	<i>Brugia malayi</i>	Increase in PAI-1 transcription	ESP	Microfilaria, adult		11035752
Unnamed protease	<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	PA (g)	Somatic, ESP	Trophozoites		2869098
VAL18	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	PLG-R	ESP	Cercaria, schistosomula	Migration, invasion	29477861

38 The interaction between *Trypanosoma cruzi* and *T. evansi* with the fibrinolytic system has also been shown *in vitro*;
39 however, these studies are not listed in this table because the identities of fibrinolysis-interacting proteins were not
40 determined (Almeida *et al.*, 2004; Acosta *et al.*, 2016). Blank cells indicate information that was not reported in the
41 publication. (a) A specific location or development stage does not necessarily indicate that the interaction is undetectable
42 in others; rather, it may also reflect that non-specified fractions/stages were not analysed in the publication. (b) Biological
43 process attributed to the interaction, whether experimentally demonstrated or not. (c) PubMed identification number. (d)
44 Fibrinolysis refers to the ability of the parasite to degrade surrounding fibrin clots that would otherwise lead to

45 immobilization, which is particularly relevant for parasites residing inside the vascular system. (e) The interaction was
46 studied *in silico* using different bioinformatics-based molecular modelling techniques. (f) PLG interaction was identified
47 by IP-MS, which revealed multiple interacting proteins; only HSP60 is included here for simplicity. (g) The authors state
48 that the identified protease is capable of activating PLG; however, supporting data are not presented. NAPc2,
49 anticoagulant protein c2; FBAL, fructose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase; GAPDH, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate
50 dehydrogenase; GST, glutathione S-transferase; HSP60, heat shock protein 60; LACK, *Leishmania* homolog of receptors
51 for activated C-kinase; PGM, phosphoglycerate mutase; SMP-1, small myristoylated protein 1; SP2, serine protease 2;
52 VAL18, venom allergen-like protein 18; TGH-2, transforming growth factor β homolog; PLG-R, plasminogen receptor;
53 ESP, excreted/secreted product; t-PA, tissue-type plasminogen activator; u-PA, urokinase-type plasminogen activator;
54 NEJ, newly-excysted juvenile; ALF, angiostatin-like fragments.